

E-Commerce: Competitive Advantage for Business Sustainability

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: December

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Shruthi, R & Swathi, M. "E-Commerce: Competitive Advantage for Business Sustainability." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 103–108.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2532957>

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Abstract

E-commerce business significantly affects business expenses and profitability. E-Commerce business has an opportunity to be broadly received because of its basic applications. In this way it has a substantial monetary affect. Electronic Commerce gives the ability of purchasing and offering items and data on the web and other on-line benefit. Electronic trade or internet business alludes to an extensive variety of online business exercises for items and administrations. Electronic trade is changing the commercial center by changing firm's plans of action, by shaping relations among showcase performers, and by adding to changes in advertise structure. It is hard to single out the impact of electronic trade Electronic business makes the likelihood of new models for arranging creation and transacting business, by offering entombs methodology and reciprocally – not just substitution – in plans of action.

E-commerce business assumes an essential part in the monetary development and improvement of country. It is an intentional action which incorporates into arranging, controlling, advancement and furthermore dispersion of different products and ventures. It additionally relates to any type of business exchange in which the gatherings collaborate electronically as opposed to by physical trades or direct physical contact.

Competitive Edge is the fact that the company has an advantage over its competitors and sustainability is the ability to continue at a particular level for a period of time. Achieving this two would be core objective of all the company.

E-commerce presents opportunities to accelerate business processes, reduce costs, reach new customers and develop new business models and markets in the business organization.

Keywords: E-commerce, competition, sustainability

Introduction

In the world of IT and BT with the globalization as a highlighter has witnessed an huge advancement in technology for change in the world market including trade, commerce, banking and marketing. It reduces the complete cost of creating and finishing paper based information.

There is customer empowerment with a change in commerce and marketing. As e-commerce is the process of exchanging product, like

wise buying and selling of products, services and information via computer networks including the internet. It requires application of internet for smooth process of business outflow and delivery of required information in terms of products, services, or payments. It does not require any publicity and advertisement in any mode as it is known and spread worldwide.

Commerce being an embracing subject in the concept of trade, “exchange of merchandise on a large scale between different countries.”

The impact of e-commerce is that it covers the whole sector of telecommunications, commercial infrastructure at the macro- environmental level. All these elements interact together to provide the fundamentals of e-commerce. Business, on the other hand, is defined as ‘a commercial enterprise as a going concern’. E-business can broadly be defined as the processes or areas involved in the running and operation of an organization that are electronic or digital in nature. It also includes marketing, sales, human resource accounting and human resource management but also indirect activities such as business process re-engineering and change management, which impact on the improvement in efficiency and integration of business processes and activities.

Literature Review

Much work and debate are going on with reference to e-commerce many researchers all over the world are studying e-commerce and its impact on business.

A study by Elizabeth Goldsmith and Sue L.T. McGregor (2000) has analyzed the impact of e-commerce on consumers, public policy, business and education. A discussion of public policy initiatives, research questions and ideas for future research are given.

A study by Andrew D. Mitchell (2001) examined the key issues that electronic commerce poses for Global trade, using as a starting point the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS), the World Trade organization (WTO) agreement most relevant to e-commerce.

A study by Jackie Gilbert Bette Ann Stead (2001) reviewed the incredible growth of electronic commerce (e-commerce) and presented ethical issues that have emerged. Security concerns, spamming, Web sites that do not carry an “advertising” label, cyber squatters, online marketing to children, conflicts of interest, manufacturers competing with intermediaries online, and “dinosaurs” were discussed.

Need and Significance of the Study

Understanding the importance of e-commerce in today’s business and impact of e-commerce in Providing competitive edge to business. Determining the present and future requirements of e-commerce for effective business transactions

Objective of the Study

- To assess the perception of vendors on E-Commerce implication in their business
- To determine the impact of E-Commerce in attracting customers
- To determine the quality of competitive edge provided by E-Commerce against competitors

Scope of the Study

This study can be useful to vendors to know how far they are comfortable using e-commerce in their business. It will also help to know the customers perspectives on developing trends in transaction of business. This study mainly focuses on e-commerce acting as competitive edge in competitive world for sustainable business development.

Limitation of the Study

- The data provided may mostly depend on perception of the vendors
- the study is based on limited number of vendors
- The observation depends on their general awareness on e-commerce utilities.

Research Methodology

It is a social research based on primary and secondary data with proper findings and analysis. Primary data was collected through the questionnaires and interviews of vendors across Bangalore city using random sampling method, secondary data was collected from websites. Samples of 100 respondents were taken for this study. Simple tools like pie charts, bar graph were used for analysis and interpretation of data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Showing Variations in Sales Post Implementation of E-Commerce

Variations in sales post implementation of E-commerce	Increase in sales post implementing E-commerce in business	Decrease in sales post implementing E-commerce in business	Neutral	Total
Percentage of Respondents	76	5	19	100

Source: Primary Data

Chart 1

Source: Excel Output

Interpretation

Table.1 Depicts that about 76% of the vendors feel that there is increase in sales post implementing e-commerce in their business, as most of the customers prefer e commerce because of ease and convenience in dealing with business transactions and hence sales are increasing. 5% of the vendors review that there is decrease in sales as most of the customers do not trust E-Commerce mode and rest 19% of the vendors review that there sales are either increasing nor decreasing they don't feel any change in the business post implementing e commerce.

Table 2: Showing the Impact of E-Commerce in Retaining Customers

Impact of E-Commerce in retaining customers	Yes E-Commerce is useful in retaining customers	No E-Commerce is not useful in retaining customers	May Be	Total
Percentage of Respondents	80	7	13	100

Source: Primary Data

Chart 2

Source: Excel Output

Interpretation

Table. 2 From the above chart it can be analyzed that about 80% of the vendors review due to implication of E-Commerce in their business they can retain the customers and serve them better 7% of the vendors review they could not retain the customers as some of the customers do not prefer using E -Commerce and the rest 13% of the vendor’s are in neutral position they do not feel any change in their business.

Table 3 Showing the Advantage of E-Commerce for Business Over its Competitors

The advantage of E-Commerce for business over its competitors	Yes E-commerce has out shown business from their competitors	No E-commerce has not out shown business from their competitors	May Be
Percentage of Respondents	85	6	9

Source: Primary Data

Chart 3

Source: Excel Output

Interpretation

Table. 3 from the above chart it can be analyzed that about 85% of the vendors feel that E-Commerce has out shown their business in front of their competitors so implication of E-Commerce has advantage over its competitors as there will be more of customers who prefer E-commerce in today's world. The rest 6 % of the vendors review that there is no such advantage customers still prefer traditional method and 9% of the vendors are in neutral position they do not feel any difference from traditional and E-Commerce business.

Findings

From the above study it has been found that

1. About 76% of the vendors feel that there is increase in sales post implementing e commerce in their business it is preferred by most of the customers.
2. 5% of the vendors review that there is decrease in sales as most of the customers do not trust e commerce mode.
3. 19% of the vendors review that there sales are neither increasing nor decreasing they don't feel any change in the business post implementing e commerce.
4. About 80% of the vendors review due to implication of E-Commerce in their business they can retain the customers and serve them better.
5. 7% of the vendors review they could not retain the customers as some of the customers do not prefer using e commerce
6. About 85% of the vendors feel that E-Commerce has out shown their business in front of their competitors.
7. 6 % of the vendors review that there is no such advantage customers still prefer traditional method
8. About 9% of the vendors are in neutral position they do not feel any difference from traditional and e commerce business

Suggestions

The present research work entitled sustaining a Competitive Advantage in the Changing Business Scenario in the field of E -Commerce has been carried out with the objective of assessing the

importance of E- Commerce in changing business scenario. The finding revealed that about 76% of the vendors review that there is increase in sales after implementing E-Commerce in their business .80% of the vendors are confident on retaining their customers due to E commerce when it comes to competition over its competitors about 85% of the vendors agree the fact that E-Commerce has out shown their business in front of their competitors.

Therefore the e- commerce has become the nerve of today's business it is more critical to emphasize on the importance of e commerce with the government plans and regulations and by ways of using it. Creating awareness about the benefits and usage of e commerce would enhance the productivity and growth of the nation in the long run

Conclusion

All in all, the present organizations should dependably endeavor to make the following best thing that buyers will need since buyers keep on desiring their items, administrations and so on to constantly be better, speedier, and less expensive. In this universe of new innovation, organizations need to suit to the new sorts of customer needs and patterns since it will end up being imperative to their business' prosperity and survival. Web based business is persistently advancing and is ending up increasingly imperative to organizations as innovation keeps on progressing and is something that ought to be exploited and actualized.

From the beginning of the Internet and E-Commerce, the conceivable outcomes have turned out to be endless for both businesses and consumers. Creating more opportunities for profit and advancements for businesses, while creating more options for consumers

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